

Learning Styles as a Correlate of Achievement of Students in Mathematics It's Implication to Classroom Teaching Learning Process

Sadiya Siddiq¹ & Anil Kumar K²

1. Research Scholar, Regional Institute of Education (NCERT), Mysuru,
Email: sadisiddiq90@gmail.com
2. Professor of Education, Regional Institute of Education (NCERT), Mysuru,
Email: dranilkumar67@gmail.com

Received : 03/02/2022

1st BPR : 12/02/2022

2nd BPR : 26/02/2022

Accepted : 03/03/2022

Abstract

Students' achievement in Mathematics is very influential for achieving success in all other subjects. Mathematics is having its application in almost all other disciplines. Mathematics is used all over the world as an essential tool in natural science, social science, engineering, medicine, etc. As Mathematics is abstract and it needs skills to understand and logical reasoning to solve problems which all individuals may not possess and it can become the hurdle in achieving their goals. The present study helps us to find out the different Mathematical abilities which are essential for achievement in Mathematics. One such ability is learning styles of students. Individual's learning styles plays an important role in achievement in various subjects at the school and postgraduate level. The knowledge of students' learning styles would help the teachers and counselors to select appropriate teaching techniques. The purpose of the study was to find out the relationship between learning styles of students and achievement in Mathematics in postgraduate course under the University of Mysore. The sample selected for the study consists of 80 postgraduate students who were pursuing M.Sc Mathematics by using simple random sampling technique. The study followed survey method under educational research. Learning styles inventory of Kolb by Peter Honey and Alan Mumford (2006) which categorizes the learning styles of students under four categories, namely activists, reflectors, theorists and pragmatist learning styles was used for assessing the learning styles and analyzing its influence on classroom teaching learning process. The findings of the study reveals that the learning styles of students vary and majority of students are reflectors, followed by pragmatist, theorist and activists were few. The analysis of the data further reveals that male and female students do not differ in their learning styles, and there is a high correlation between the learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of postgraduate students. This study implies that students will have various styles and multi-faced approach in learning. This has to be understood by the teachers and other practitioners to improve the students learning Process as well as to improve the quality of Education.

Keywords: Learning Styles, Achievement in Mathematics, Teaching Learning Process.

Introduction:

Students' achievement in Mathematics is very influential for achieving success in other subjects and classroom teaching learning process. Mathematics is having its application in almost all other disciplines. Mathematics is used all over the world as an essential tool in natural science, social science, engineering, medicine, etc. The knowledge of students' learning styles would help the teachers and counselors to select appropriate teaching techniques. Mathematics is important not just

in the education of scientists, engineers and economists but also in the education of each and every individual in society. The importance of Mathematics in developing formulas and models that explain the physical characteristics of the universe is well known. It is a basic subject of study in engineering and medicine to discover and treat the diseases as well. It also plays a key role in the development of new rules, principles and theories and discovering new planets in science. Perhaps in the social sciences and languages too it is having its role. Hence improving the achievement in Mathematics should be the focus of all the classroom teaching learning process.

Learning is an important indispensable part of Education and in every stage of a person's life, for their moral, emotional, ethical, social and personal development. Learning is the process of acquiring new, or modifying existing knowledge, behaviors, skills, values, or preferences. Learning is something we do every day: at home, at school, through the internet, at work. Everyone learns differently, it makes sense that different learners follow different and individualistic learning styles. Learning styles may play an important role in achievement at postgraduate level and classroom teaching learning process. Learning styles refer to the variations in ability to accumulate as well as assimilate information.

The term *learning styles* is widely used to describe how learners gather, sift through, interpret, organize, come to conclusions about, and "store" information for further use. A learning style is a student's consistent way of responding to and using stimuli in the context of learning.

Keefe (1979) defines learning styles as the "composite of characteristic cognitive, affective, and physiological factors that serve as relatively stable indicators of how a learner perceives, interacts with, and responds to the learning environment."

Stewart and Felicetti (1992) define learning styles as those "educational conditions under which a student is most likely to learn." Thus, learning styles are not really concerned with *what* learners learn, but rather *how* they prefer to learn.

Learning styles are a set of methods used most efficiently to acquire new information. Basically, learning styles is the method that allows gathering and using knowledge in a specific manner. Each individual may possess single styles or could possess a combination of many learning styles. Kolb is the psychologist who tried to identify and categorize learning styles and its components with the specific behavior patterns of individuals possessing different learning styles. According to his theory of Learning Styles, the categories of the Learning Styles are a. Activist, b. Reflector, c. Theorist and d. Pragmatist.

Honey and Mumford's Learning Styles Questionnaire

Kolb is the inspiration for a large numbers of theorists. For example, Honey and Mumford's model, *Learning Styles Questionnaire (LSQ)*, is directly derived from Kolb's theory. Their model looks similar to this:

Learning Styles: The categories and general descriptions of learning styles given by Kolb are;

Activist:

They Prefer the challenges of new experiences, involvement with others, assimilation and role-playing. Likes anything new, problem solving, and small group discussions.

Activists involve themselves fully and without bias in new experiences.

They enjoy the here and now and are happy to be dominated by immediate experiences.

They are open-minded, not sceptical and this tends to make them enthusiastic about anything new.

Their philosophy is: 'I'll try anything once'.

They tend to act first and consider the consequences afterwards.

Their days are filled with activity.

They tackle problems by brainstorming.

As soon as the excitement from one activity has died down they are busy looking for the next.

They tend to thrive on the challenge of new experiences but are bored with implementation and longer term consolidation.

They are gregarious people constantly involving themselves with others but, in doing so, they seek to centre all activities around themselves.

Reflectors:

Prefers to learn from activities that allow them to watch, think, and review (time to think things over) what has happened.

Like to use journals and brain storming. Lectures are helpful if they provide expert explanations and analysis.

They like to stand back and ponder experiences and observe them from many different perspectives.

They collect data, both first hand and from others, and prefer to think about it thoroughly before coming to any conclusion.

The thorough collection and analysis of data about experiences and events is what counts so they tend to postpone reaching definitive conclusions for as long as possible.

Their philosophy is to be cautious.

They are thoughtful people who like to consider all possible angles and implications before making a move.

They prefer to take a back seat in meetings and discussions.

They enjoy observing other people in action.

They listen to others and get the drift of the discussion before making their own points.

They tend to adopt a low profile and have a slightly distant, tolerant unruffled air about them.

When they act it is part of a wide picture which includes the past as well as the present and others' observations as well as their own.

Theorist:

They Prefer to think problems through in a step-by-step manner.

Likes lectures, analogies, systems, case studies, models and readings.

Talking with experts is normally not helpful.

They adapt and integrate observations into complex but logically sound theories.

They think problems through in a vertical, step by step, logical way.

They assimilate disparate facts into coherent theories.

They tend to be perfectionists who won't rest easy until things are tidy and fit into a rational scheme.

They like to analyse and synthesise.

They are keen on basic assumptions, principles, theories, models and systems thinking.

Their philosophy prizes rationality and logic.

If it's logical it's good'.

Questions they frequently ask are: 'Does it make sense?' 'How does this fit with that?' 'What are the basic assumptions?'

They tend to be detached, analytical and dedicated to rational objectivity rather than anything subjective or ambiguous.

Their approach to problems is consistently logical.

This is their 'mental set' and they rigidly reject anything that doesn't fit with it.

They prefer to maximise certainty and feel uncomfortable with subjective judgements, lateral thinking and anything flippant.

Pragmatist:

They Prefer to apply new learning to actual practice to see if they work.

Likes laboratories, field work, and observations. Likes feedback, coaching and obvious links between the task-on-hand and a problem.

They are keen on trying out ideas, theories and techniques to see if they work in practice.

They positively search out new ideas and take the first opportunity to experiment with applications.

They are the sort of people who return from management courses brimming with new ideas that they want to try out in practice.

They like to get on with things and act quickly and confidently on ideas that attract them.

They tend to be impatient with ruminating and opened discussions.

They are essentially practical, down to earth people who like making practical decisions and solving problems.

They respond to problems and opportunities 'as a challenge'.

Their philosophy is: There is always a better way' and 'If it works it's good'.

Need and Significance of study:

As Mathematics is abstract and it needs skills to understand and logical reasoning to solve problems which all individuals may not possess and it can become the hurdle in achieving their goals. Hence, this study was planned to find out the different components and abilities which may be essential for achievement in Mathematics such as learning styles, which plays an important role in achievement at Post-graduate level, thus, giving implications for improvement in the classroom teaching learning process. Hence, this study helps us to find out the different abilities which may be essential for achievement in Mathematics and influential for classroom teaching learning process. One such ability is learning styles of students. Griggs and Dunn (1996) claim that students who learn from an approach compatible with their preferred learning styles experience greater academic achievement and have a more positive attitude towards learning. Moreover, Dunn, Beaudry and Klavas (2011) asserted that through voluminous studies, it has been indicated that both low and average achievers earn higher scores on standardized achievement tests when they are taught within the realm of their learning styles. Abidin, Rezaee, Abdullah, & Singh, (2011) found significant relationship between overall academic achievement and learning styles. Vaishnav(2013) also found that there exist positive high correlation between learning styles and academic achievement.

The purpose of the present study was to find out the relationship between different learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of students studying in post-graduation course under University of Mysore. The knowledge of students learning styles would help the teachers to select appropriate teaching techniques which may help the students to improve their academic performance.

Objectives of the study:

The following were the objectives of the study;

To find the learning styles of Post- graduate students.

To study the relationship between learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of Post- graduate students.

Hypotheses of the study:

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study;

- There is no significant difference in the learning styles of boys and girls students.

- There is no relationship between learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of students at Post- graduate level.

Design and sampling of the study:

Survey method was employed for conducting the present study to find the relationship between learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of Post- graduate students. The population of the study consists of all the post graduate students pursuing M.Sc in Mathematics during the academic year 2014-2015. There were 250 students of M.Sc Mathematics, under University of Mysore. Out of this, 80 students have been selected by using simple random sampling technique. The sample consists of Post- graduate students of Department of Studies in Mathematics, Manasagangothri, Maharani's Science College for Women, and Yuvaraja's College of Mysore.

Tools used for data collection:

- a. **Learning styles inventory of Kolb by Peter Honey and Alan Mumford (2006)** was used to assess the learning styles of Mathematics Post- graduate students.

The categories and general descriptions of learning styles given by Kolb are as follows;

Reflector - Prefers to learn from activities that allow them to watch, think, and review (time to think things over) what has happened. Likes to use journals and brainstorming. Lectures are helpful if they provide expert explanations and analysis.

Theorist - Prefer to think problems through in a step-by-step manner. Likes lectures, analogies, systems, case studies, models, and readings. Talking with experts is normally not helpful.

Pragmatist - Prefers to apply new learnings to actual practice to see if they work. Likes laboratories, field work, and observations. Likes feedback, coaching, and obvious links between the task-on-hand and a problem.

Activist - Prefers the challenges of new experiences, involvement with others, assimilation and role-playing. Likes anything new, problem solving, and small group discussions.

- b. **Achievement scores:** The result of previous semester (2nd semester) final marks of Post-graduate students has been considered as the scores for Achievement in Mathematics.

Travers (1970: 447) states that **achievement** is the result of what an individual has learned from some educational experiences. Additionally, De Cecco & Crawford (1977) states that **achievement** is the expectancy of finding satisfaction in mastering challenging and difficult performances.

Statistical techniques for analysis of data:

The data were analyzed using percentage analysis, chi square and correlation statistical techniques such as bi-serial correlation.

Percentage analysis: This has been used to evaluate the percentage of learning style according to their components respectively to know the status of learning style of post graduate students.

Chi- square: This statistical technique has been used to find if there is any significant difference in the gender and learning style of post graduate students.

Correlation co efficient: The bi-serial co-efficient of correlation has been used to find the relationship and association between the learning styles and achievement of post graduate students.

Results:

I. Learning styles of Post- graduate students.

The Kolb's Learning Styles Inventory was administered for the sample students of the study and the categorization of the learning styles and their percentage analysis are shown in table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Percentage analysis of categorization of learning styles components.

Learning styles	Activist	Reflector	Theorist	Pragmatist	Total
Frequency(f)	12	32	16	20	80
Percentage(%)	15%	40%	20%	25%	100%

The above table reveals that 15% of students have activist learning styles, 40% belongs to reflectors, 20% belong to theorist and 25% belong to pragmatist category of learning styles. Thus, it reveals that majority of students belongs to the reflector category of learning styles. A Graphical representation of the above result is provided in Fig 1.

Fig 1: Percentage analysis of categories of learning styles.

II. Classification of Learning Styles based on gender

The gender wise difference in the Learning styles of post- graduate students was analyzed by using chi-square and it is represented in Table 1.2

Table 1.2: Chi-square table for association between learning styles and gender of Post- graduate students.

Variables	Chi-square (χ^2) value	Degrees of freedom	Table value	Significance
Learning styles	6.926	3	7.82	Not significant
Gender				

The above table reveals that the obtained chi-square value 6.926 is lesser than the table value of 7.82 at 0.05 level of significance for degree of freedom 3. Hence, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference in the learning styles of boys and girls students” is accepted and it is concluded that, male and female post-graduate students do not differ in their learning styles.

III. Relationship between learning styles and achievement of Post- graduate students

The learning styles and its relation with achievement scores of post- graduate students was analyzed using bi-serial correlation and it is represented in table 1.3

Table 1.3: Bi-serial coefficient for relationship between learning styles and achievement female Post

Variables	Co-efficient of Correlation	r-value	Interpretation
Learning styles	Bi-serial	0.9316	Very High Correlation
Achievement			

The above table reveals that the r value is 0.9316 (> 0.5) is having very high correlation. Hence, the null hypothesis “There is no correlation between learning styles and achievement of Post- graduate students” is rejected and it is concluded that there is a very high correlation between learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of Post- graduate students.

Discussions:

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of learning styles on achievement in Mathematics at Post-graduate level and its implications for classroom teaching learning process. By considering the data collected from Post-graduate students of Mathematics, the following major considerations are drawn from analysis and interpretation of data.

The percentage analysis of learning styles of sample reveals 15% belongs to activist, 40% belongs to reflectors, 20% belong to theorist and 25% belong to pragmatist category of learning styles according to Kolb's learning styles. Majority of the students belongs to Reflector category of Learning styles.

The chi-square analysis of learning styles and gender reveals that male and female Post-graduate students do not differ in their learning styles.

The bi-serial co-efficient of correlation reveals that there is very high correlation between learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of Post-graduate students.

The study is also in concern with the studies carried out by Griggs and Dunn (1996) claim that students who learn from an approach compatible with their preferred learning styles experience greater academic achievement and have a more positive attitude towards learning. Moreover, Dunn, Beaudry and Klavas (2011) asserted that through voluminous studies, it has been indicated that both low and average achievers earn higher scores on standardized achievement tests when they are taught within the realm of their learning styles. Abidin, Rezaee, Abdullah, & Singh, (2011) found significant relationship between overall academic achievement and learning styles. Vaishnav(2013) also found that there exist positive high correlation between learning styles and academic achievement.

Implications of the study:

The study revealed the status of learning styles of Post-graduate students. After identifying which learning styles the majority of students have, there is a need to provide awareness regarding the learning styles to the teachers, so as to plan their instruction accordingly.

As the findings of the study reveals that, there is a very high correlation between learning styles and achievement in Mathematics of Post-graduate students, which implies the achievement can be improved by facilitating the students to adopt proper and suitable learning styles during the teaching learning process. Thus, it can be concluded that the achievement in Mathematics among students can be improved by observing, modifying and utilizing the preferred learning styles of students.

References

- Best J.W (1986). *Research in education*. Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi
- Buch M.B (1991). *Fourth survey of research in education. Volume 1 (1983-1988)*. NCERT, New Delhi.
- Sumangala (1995). *Some psychological variables discriminating between high and low achievers in Mathematics*. Experiments in Education.
- Afifa Tanvir (2012). *Relationship between study habits and academic achievement among hostel living and day scholar*. UK. British journal of humanities and social sciences.
- Borasi. R (1987). *Exploring Mathematics Through the Analysis of Errors*. For the Learning of Mathematics- An International Journal of Mathematics Education 7, 3:2-8
- Abidin, M. J. Z., Rezaee, A. A., Abdullah, H. N., & Singh, K. K. B. (2011). Learning Styles and Overall Academic Achievement in a Specific Educational System. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*.
- Vaishnav, R. (2013). Learning Styles and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. *Voice of Research*.
- Tuan LT. *EFL learners' learning styles and their attributes*. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 2011; 2 (2): 299-320.
- Griggs S, Dunn R; *Hispanic-American students and learning styles*. East Lansing, MI: National Center for Research on Teacher Learning. ERIC Document Reproduction Service no. 1996ED 393607
- Coffield, F., Moseley, D., Hall, E., & Ecclestone, K. (2004). *Learning styles and pedagogy in post-16 learning: A systematic and critical review*. www.LSRC.ac.uk: Learning and Skills Research Centre. Retrieved January, 15, 2008: <http://www.lsd.org.uk/files/PDF/1543.pdf>
- Honey, P. & Mumford, A. (2000). *The learning styles helper's guide*. Maidenhead: Peter Honey Publications Ltd.

